

Negative consequences of procrastination in students

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Annotation. This article provides a general understanding of procrastination, information about the manifestations, causes and solutions of procrastination in students. Postponing an important task that needs to be done is called procrastination in psychology.

Keywords: procrastination, stress, laziness, personality trait pressure.

Intoduction. Today, time is moving so fast that time has become an important factor. Global competition has made the timeliness of work execution a critical factor, along with the quality of the work that needs to be done. As time becomes a major factor, procrastination is also becoming more common. While this situation may occur due to laziness in some people, it may occur due to lack of experience in others. Postponing something that needs to be done is something that happens to everyone. Regularly postponing necessary tasks leads to negative consequences. Postponing necessary work is called procrastination in psychology.

Methodology. The content of the article consists of theoretical information. The manifestations of procrastination in students have been studied mainly through a separate questionnaire. The article was not cited because it has not yet published. The section on the negative consequences and recommendations of procrastination in students includes various sources, as well as the author's subjective opinions.

The main part. There has been a lot of research done on procrastination (Fuschia Sirois, Joseph Ferrari, Piers Steel, Timothy Pychyl).

A number of researches have provided their own definitions of procrastination. These include:

Piers Steel - "Procrastination is the deliberate postponement or postponement of necessary and important jobs, even though one knows that negative consequences will outweigh the positive ones".[2]

Lay - "the trait of procrastination - the tendency to postpone something necessary to achieve a goal".[1]

Procrastination, according to researchers, can be defined as follows: procrastination is the voluntary, conscious, and unreasonably postponing of necessary and important work, knowing the negative consequences.[3]

Procrastination is most common among students[2]. Procrastination in students can manifest in a variety of ways. These include:

- delays submission of internship documents;
- delays completion of coursework;
- delays submission of independent work;
- arrives late for classes;
- fails to complete notes on time;
- fails to complete homework;
- comes to practice and seminar classes unprepared;
- delays bedtime;
- fails to pay attention to health on time;

-fails to fulfill promises made to others.

Procrastination among students leads to completing unfinished assignments at the end of the year. Completing too many tasks at the same time requires a lot of resources from the student. There can be various reasons for procrastination in students. These include:

- reasons related to personality trait: lack of willpower, laziness, irresponsibility, hesitation in making decisions, dislike of work, frequent sleep, perfectionism;
- psychological reasons: fear, anxiety, shame, stress, excitement, mood, lack of motivation;
- related to the physical condition of the person: fatigue, stress, lack of sleep;
- health problems;
- social reasons: a lot of work other than studying, spending a lot of time with friends, relatives and acquaintances. Presence of work other than studying.
 - related to skills: lack of experience and knowledge, inability to find the necessary information or not knowing how to find it, inability to organize work;
 - inability to properly distribute time: thinking that I still have time, spending a lot of time on unnecessary things, inability to properly distribute time between tasks;
 - attitude to the task: dislike of the task, time-consuming, difficult task, boring;
 - distractions: phone, internet, games.

When procrastination occurs regularly in students, it can lead to a number of negative consequences. In this case, the students experiences high psychological, physical and social pressure. The negative consequences of procrastination include:

- causes low grades[6];
- fails to pass the next course;
- absents in classes;
- loss of trust in the student;
- decreased self-confidence[6];
- constant stress and pressure;
- experiencing shame, guilt, sadness;
- loss of interest;
- inability to acquire professional skills;
- increased confusion;
- the quality of the acquired knowledge decreases.
- economic damage;
- paying extra credit and retaking the course;
- lack of sleep;
- receiving many warnings from the teacher;
- increases susceptibility to heart disease[6];
- causes digestive problems[6];
- weakens the immune system[6];
- may cause insomnia[6];

Although the term procrastination is a new concept, a lot of work has been done on procrastination in a short time. Researchers have developed a number of recommendations aimed at preventing and reducing procrastination as a result of studying it. These are the followings:

- break the task into as small as possible parts[6];
- set a clear goal[6];
- determine how much time each small task will take[6];
- focus only on the current task[6];
- know the limits of your capabilities[6];
- be aware of the situation[4];
- develop skills of proper time distribution;
- complete tasks on time;
- set a specific time for the task;
- develop skills of working with information;
- develop self-management skills;
- solve health-related issues;
- limit unnecessary things [4];
- get help with difficult issues;
- ask teachers for things they don't understand, clarify tasks;
- get enough sleep;
- keep work and study space tidy;
- keep distractions away while studying.

It is also important to take out from time to time to relax by engaging in your interests and hobbies[4].

Conclusion. Procrastination is a common occurrence among students. Therefore, it is important to teach students how to properly organize their study process. Given that one of the most common causes of procrastination is work-related stress, it is important to increase students' interest and motivation for studying. There is currently a lot of research being conducted on procrastination in students and studying it in the future will help solve study-related issues.

References

1. Schouvenburg, Genri "Counseling procrastinators in academic settings". Washington, DC: American Psychological Association. 2004
2. P.Steel "Nature of procrastination"//Psychological Bulletin. January 2007. 133(1):6594
3. S.Ismailov "Prokrastinatsiya hodisasini o'rganishning ayrim dolzarb masalalari"//Sciencebox.uz. 28.12.2024. Vol.22
4. Wikipediya
5. www.Solvingprocrastination.com
6. www.procrastinus.com